

EMPOWERING YOUTH: STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING LEGAL CULTURE AMONG YOUTH

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Annotation: In this article, the importance of enhancing legal culture as a crucial factor in social and political relations is discussed, with a systematic analysis of the processes related to forming legal culture within the political-legal system of society. The focus is also on justifying the connection between national development, the stability of the political-legal system of society, and the processes of establishing principles of peace and justice. Additionally, the article is dedicated to a systematic study of how constitutions and laws serve as the legal basis for maintaining social balance, which requires social cohesion and mutual compromise, and how a legal culture based on the rule of law is also linked to the social-political organization of society.

Key words: society, justice, tolerance, spirituality, enlightenment, tradition, culture, democracy, literacy, education.

Legal culture serves to instill in our consciousness values such as justice and legality, respect and attention towards individuals, patience and tolerance, based on the ancient traditions, customs, language, religion, and spirit of our people. Therefore, elevating legal culture, which directs people's thoughts and worldview towards dedicated work for our independence, is a vital necessity. Improving the legal culture and legal awareness of the population, enhancing legal education and enlightenment, fundamentally improving the organization of legal knowledge in society, fostering a profound respect and reverence for human rights and freedoms, instilling a sense of obedience to the law, and ensuring adherence to and knowledge of the law are essential demands of today. In the process of building a legal democratic state and a just civil society, shaping the legal consciousness and legal culture of each citizen is considered a fundamental and important task [1]. Legal culture is an integral part of general culture, encompassing individuals' level of legal knowledge, their conscious attitude towards the law, and their respect for and adherence to legal norms.

Uzbekistan is firmly establishing itself in the global community by building a democratic rule-of-law state and forming a just civil society. The development of our country and the success of reforms are largely dependent on the level of the people's legal culture. In this regard, the "National Program for Enhancing

Legal Culture in Society” states the following: “A high level of legal culture is both the foundation of a democratic society and a reflection of the maturity of the legal system. It actively influences various life processes in society, helps in the cohesion of citizens and all social groups, and is a factor in ensuring and strengthening societal unity and order. Respect for the law is one of the fundamental requirements for the effective functioning of a legal society, as well as for political and legal systems” [2].

This program provides a detailed overview of the principles of state policy in the field of shaping and enhancing legal culture, the main tasks for achieving this goal, and the priority directions of state policy in shaping legal culture. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has appropriately assessed the historical significance of the program and emphasizes the following: “The current era necessitates the revision of the national program adopted twenty years ago. I believe it is appropriate for our Parliament to lead the creation of a new national program for enhancing legal culture in society” [3].

For this purpose, without much delay, on January 9, 2019, the President’s Decree “On Fundamental Improvement of the System for Enhancing Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Society” was issued, and based on this decree, the “Concept for Enhancing Legal Culture in Society” was adopted [4]. To elaborate on the concept, its primary goal is to create a comprehensive and systematic approach to ensure that all layers of the population achieve legal literacy. This includes fostering citizens who are determined, aware of their rights, respectful of the law, able to apply their legal knowledge in daily life, possess an active civic stance, and maintain a zero-tolerance attitude towards legal violations.

The legal maturity of a state is determined by the level of legal literacy among its population. Moreover, possessing legal knowledge and legal culture is one of the virtues characteristics of a socially active and highly cultured person. In this context, it is worth mentioning the following thoughts of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “No matter how perfect our laws are or how many reforms we implement, achieving the expected results will be difficult if our citizens’ legal awareness and culture are insufficient” [3]. Indeed, when citizens have an understanding of the law and its implications, a sense of responsibility also develops in them. It is essential to explain to each citizen, based on norms of decency and morality, what is good, what is bad, what is permissible, and what is not, using concepts of rights and duties, honesty, and integrity. Teaching them the most important principles of our fundamental law, the Constitution, in a

language they can understand from a young age, and instilling these principles in their consciousness, will contribute to increasing the level of legal literacy in the population.

In shaping and promoting legal culture in society, it is important to focus on the following:

- fundamentally improving legal education and the promotion of legal knowledge in our country;
- ensuring that each normative-legal document is effectively communicated to its implementers;
- broadly informing the public about the objectives and content of newly adopted laws;
- increasing the number of competitions and events aimed at enhancing legal knowledge;
- enhancing legal education, as well as developing and improving the training and qualification system for legal professionals;
- strengthening the role of mass media in providing legal information, extensively using innovative methods of legal promotion, including expanding the use of web technologies;
- conducting in-depth research into the scientific foundations of enhancing legal awareness and legal culture in society [5].

In conclusion, the formation of legal culture in society is a systematic process, and the social and political factors affecting the issue are closely linked not only to citizens' attitudes towards the law but also to the legitimacy of the executive and law enforcement sectors.

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